

MYOMA DISEASE, ITS SYMPTOMS AND PREVENTION

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Abstract. *This article provides information about myoma, its causes, and its prevention.*

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Uterine myoma is a tumor growth of the connective tissue and muscle fibers of the uterus. Uterine fibroids are common growths of the uterus. They often appear during the years when you can get pregnant and give birth. Uterine fibroids are not cancerous and they rarely become cancerous. They are also not associated with a higher risk of other types of uterine cancer. They are also called **leiomyomas or fibroids**.

Symptoms of the disease:

- **Heavy menstrual bleeding or painful periods.**
- **Longer or more frequent periods.**
- **Pressure or pain in the pelvic area.**
- **Frequent urination or trouble urinating.**
- **Stomach area increases.**
- **Constipation.**
- **Pain in the stomach area or lower back, or pain during sex.**

Gene change. Many fibroids have gene changes that differ from normal uterine muscle cells.

Hormones. Two hormones called estrogen and progesterone cause the lining of the uterus to thicken during each menstrual period in preparation for pregnancy. These hormones also promote fibroid growth.

Risk factors

In addition to a person of reproductive age, several risk factors for uterine fibroids are known. These include:

- For racial reasons. All women of reproductive age can develop fibroids. But blacks are more likely to develop fibroids than other racial groups. Blacks have younger fibroids than whites. They are also more likely to have more or larger fibroids with worse symptoms than whites.

- Family history. If your mother or sister had fibroids, you are at a higher risk of getting them.

- Other factors. Starting menstruation before the age of 10; obesity; lack of vitamin D; the diet contains more red meat and less green vegetables, fruits and dairy products; and drinking alcohol, including beer, increases the risk of fibroids.

Uterine fibroids are often found incidentally during routine pelvic examinations. The doctor may notice irregular changes in the shape of the uterus, which indicates the presence of fibroids.

If you have symptoms of uterine fibroids, you may need the following tests:

- Ultrasound. This test uses sound waves to take a picture of the uterus. He can confirm if you have fibroids and map and measure them.

- Hysteroscopy. For this test, your doctor will insert a small, lighted telescope called a hysteroscope through your cervix into your uterus. Then a physiological solution is injected into the uterus. This expands the uterine cavity and allows the doctor to examine the walls of the uterus and the opening of the fallopian tubes.

- Hysteroscopy. Hysterosalpingography (his-tur-o-sal-ping-GOG-ruh-fee) uses dye to highlight the uterine cavity and fallopian tubes on X-ray images. If infertility is a concern, your doctor may recommend it. This test can help determine whether the fallopian tubes are open or blocked and can show some submucosal fibroids.
- Hysterosonography. Hysterosonography (his-tur-o-suh-NOG-ruh-fee) uses sterile saline, called saline, to dilate the space inside the uterus, called the uterine cavity. This makes it easier to image submucosal fibroids and the lining of the uterus if you are trying to get pregnant or have heavy menstrual bleeding. Another name for hysterosonography is saline infusion sonogram.

- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). This test can show the size and location of the fibroid in more detail. It can also detect different types of tumors and help determine treatment options. MRI is often used in people with larger uteruses or those approaching menopause, also known as perimenopause.

Disease treatment measures:

For women with symptomatic fibroids, hormonal drugs can regulate the menstrual cycle and reduce bleeding, but they do not prevent the growth of fibroid cysts. Other procedures are invasive surgery such as uterine artery embolization.

Medicines. Medicines for fibroids treat the patient's symptoms. Fibroids don't go away, but they can shrink with some medications. They can also help with symptoms such as pain and bleeding.

If the patient has mild symptoms or no symptoms at all, the doctor may recommend waiting and seeing the patient. Fibroids are not cancerous and may grow slowly or not at all. They may also shrink or disappear after menopause.

Like all diseases, fibroid disease is caused by wrong lifestyle. Therefore, a person should pay attention to his health and follow a healthy lifestyle.